

Thermochromic Behaviour of Buffered Indicator Solutions. Part-II. The System Hydrazenium sulphate—*m*-Nitrophenol

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The thermochromic behaviour of aqueous solutions containing the indicator *m*-nitrophenol and the buffer hydrazenium sulphate was investigated in the temperature range 5–55°. The optical density–temperature data were fitted to the equation, $\log R = a/T + b + cT$, where R is the ratio of base to acid forms of the indicator. Thermodynamic data pertaining to the proton ionisations of indicator and buffer were obtained directly from this equation. The results are compared with those obtained by conventional methods.

THERMOCHROMACY is a term that denotes the dependence of optical density on temperature.

In an earlier publication¹, thermochromic behaviour of phenolphthalein was investigated in four buffers and apparent molar enthalpies for the proton ionisation of this indicator were reported. Those $\Delta H'$ values, however, were essentially constant over the wide temperature range investigated and the inclusion of heat capacity terms for the ionisation processes was therefore not required. In this work, a system is selected for which the difference between the heat capacities of buffer and indicator is significant, and the treatment is extended in order to provide the relevant thermodynamic data.

For a system containing buffer HB and indicator HIn, application of the Van't Hoff relation to the two acid ionisation equilibria yields the equation,

$$\log [(a_{\text{In}^-}/a_{\text{HIn}})(a_{\text{HB}}/a_{\text{B}^-})] = -(\Delta H_{\text{B}} - \Delta H_{\text{I}})/2.303 RT + \text{constant} \quad (1)$$

on the condition that the enthalpies of ionisation for buffer and indicator, ΔH_{B} and ΔH_{I} , are independent of temperature. If the solution is studied within a narrow pH range near the pK of the buffer, then the ratio $a_{\text{HB}}/a_{\text{B}^-}$ should remain essentially invariant with temperature. Furthermore, the temperature dependence of the ratio $\gamma_{\text{In}^-}/\gamma_{\text{HIn}}$ may be overlooked. This is borne out by numerous instances in the literature, particularly the data compiled by Fasman², which indicate that the enthalpies of ionisation of many weak acids are not sensitive to ionic strength variations over a moderate range. This means that the terms $d\gamma_{\text{In}^-}/dT$ and $d\gamma_{\text{HIn}}/dT$ are both negligibly small. With these provisions, equation (1) becomes¹

$$\log R = -a/T + b \quad (2)$$

where, $R = [\text{In}^-]/[\text{HIn}]$ and $a = -(\Delta H'_{\text{B}} - \Delta H'_{\text{I}})/2.303 R$. The primed enthalpy values are apparent ones, since concentrations are employed.

Equation (2) was applied successfully to the treatment of thermochromic data obtained with the phenolphthalein-buffer systems¹, but is evidently not applicable to cases where the term $(\Delta C_{\text{B}} - \Delta C_{\text{I}})$ is significant. It is thus desirable to investigate the suitability of the thermochromic method to such systems. To this end, the buffer hydrazenium sulphate was selected because of its large reported ΔC_{p} value (*ca.* $-1.9 \text{ J K}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$)³ whereas the indicator *m*-nitrophenol was selected because of its small value (*ca.* $-0.1 \text{ J K}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$)⁴, thereby assuring a significant value for the difference in the heat capacities of ionisation, $\Delta(\Delta C_{\text{p}})$. Furthermore, for best results, the pK of the indicator should lie well within the buffering range of the buffer. This condition is met in the hydrazenium sulphate—*m*-nitrophenol system (pK° values at 25° are 8.303 for *m*-nitrophenol⁴ and 7.965 for hydrazenium sulphate⁵). Finally, the optical density of the solution must be highly sensitive to temperature and this requirement is also met.

Experimental

m-Nitrophenol and hydrazenium sulphate were recrystallised from chloroform and boiling water, respectively. pH measurements were conducted on a Beckman 4500 research type pH meter. The reliability of the measurement was better than 0.005 pH unit. The calibration of the instrument was repeated every time the temperature was altered, making use of the reported value of -0.0025 for the temperature coefficient of the phosphate buffer employed as standard. Measurements involving hydrazenium sulphate were conducted under a nitrogen atmosphere. Spectrophotometric measurements were made on a Pye-Unicam SP 8-500 spectrophotometer equipped with a thermostated cell compartment. Measurements were made in the range 5–55°, with the temperature inside the cell

monitored to within 0.1 by means of a thermocouple. Optical density readings used for the calculation of R values were those collected at 403 nm, the wavelength of maximum sensitivity to temperature changes. At this wavelength the optical density of the acidic form of the indicator is virtually zero. The ionic strength of all solutions was maintained at 0.115 M by the addition of sodium chloride.

Results and Discussion

For a proper assessment of the reliability and applicability of the thermochromic method to the present system, it is at first necessary to obtain acidity constants for buffer and indicator, in the temperature interval of interest and at the same ionic strength employed. These pK' values, obtained by potentiometric titration with 0.100 N NaOH, are listed in Table 1. A linear regression computer program was employed in order to obtain the best-fit of the data to the equation⁵,

$$pK = a/T - b + cT \quad (3)$$

The constants obtained were, for *m*-nitrophenol: $a=172.4$, $b=-0.3457$, and $c=7.330 \times 10^{-3}$; for hydrazenium sulphate: $a=5257$, $b=20.03$, and $c=3.480 \times 10^{-2}$. The apparent enthalpy and heat capacity of ionisation values for each acid may be obtained from

$$\Delta H = 2.303 R (a - cT^2) \quad (4)$$

$$\text{and } \Delta C_p = -4.606 R cT \quad (5)$$

TABLE 1— pK' VALUES FOR *m*-NITROPHENOL AND HYDRAZENIUM SULPHATE

$I=0.115 M$		
T °C	pK' (ind) (± 0.005)	pK' (buffer) (± 0.005)
5	8.592	8.556
10	8.500	8.365
15	8.427	8.243
20	8.395	8.104
25	8.315	7.980
30	8.262	7.866
35	8.179	7.766
40	8.140	7.650
45	8.086	7.572
50	8.057	7.408
55	8.003	7.319

Substitution for the constants just obtained in equation (4) yields, at 25°, $\Delta H'$ values of 20.55 and 41.38 kJ mol^{-1} for the indicator and the buffer, respectively. The reported⁴ thermodynamic value for the indicator at this temperature is 20.05 kJ mol^{-1} , close to the $\Delta H'$ value of this work. For the buffer, however, there are two literature values for ΔH° at 25°, 41.71 kJ mol^{-1} obtained calorimetrically⁶, and 44.4 kJ mol^{-1} obtained⁸ through the application of equation (3) to four pK° values at 15, 20, 25 and 35°. The value of $\Delta H'$ in this work at 25°, agrees most closely with the calorimetric value, which is itself inherently more accurate

than that obtained indirectly from pK measurements. In addition, the second ΔH° value was based on only four measurements within a narrow temperature range. This limitation is expected to introduce substantial errors in all the derived thermodynamic values⁷, particularly in ΔC_p . Thus, ΔC_p as calculated from equation (5) is $-293 \text{ J K}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ at 25° (11 pK values within a 50° interval) contrasts sharply with the reported⁸ value of $-1.9 \text{ J K}^{-1} \text{ mol}^{-1}$ (4 pK° values within a 20° interval). The comparison between the apparent and thermodynamic values for the enthalpy and heat capacity of hydrazenium sulphate is justifiable. This is demonstrated by a simple calculation based on the reported⁸ pK° and B values for the equation, $pK' = pK^\circ + BI$, where I is the ionic strength. A value of 1.60×10^{-3} may be calculated for the term dB/dT at 25°. Since

$$\Delta H' = \Delta H^\circ - 2.303 RT^2 I(dB/dT),$$

the term $(\Delta H^\circ - \Delta H')$, at 25° and $I=0.115 M$, is only 0.32 J mol^{-1} . Thus $\Delta H'$, and consequently ΔC_p values for hydrazenium sulphate are expected to deviate less than one percent upon moderate changes in the ionic strength of the medium.

Thermochromic results: The optical densities of the solutions investigated exhibited large changes with temperature. At each temperature, a value for R was obtained from the equation, $R = (D - D_a)/(D_b - D)$, where D is the optical density of the solution and D_a and D_b are the optical densities of the most acid and most basic solutions. For a typical solution containing $2.390 \times 10^{-4} M$ *m*-nitrophenol and $5.000 \times 10^{-3} M$ hydrazenium sulphate ($\text{pH}=8.174$ at 25°), the optical density at 403 nm dropped from a value of 1.280 at 5.0° to a value of 0.620 at 55.0° Fig. 1 is a plot of $\log R$ against the reciprocal of the absolute temperature for this solution. Since the points do not lie on a straight line, equation (2) may not be employed. In order to treat the data, equation (3) is written separately for buffer and indicator to yield,

$$pK_B = a_B/T - b_B + c_B T = \text{pH} - \log (a_B^-/a_{HB}) \quad (6a)$$

$$\text{and } pK_I = a_I/T - b_I + c_I T = \text{pH} - \log (a_{In}^-/a_{HIIn}) \quad (6b)$$

where the subscripts B and I refer to buffer and indicator, respectively. When equation (6b) is subtracted from (6a) and the provision of constancy of the terms (a_B^-/a_{HB}) and $(\gamma_{In}^-/\gamma_{HIIn})$ is included (see above), the following equation results,

$$\log R = a/T - b + cT \quad (7)$$

where, $a = a_B - a_I$, $b = b_B - b_I + \log (\gamma_{In}^-/\gamma_{HIIn}) (a_{HB}/a_B^-)$, and $c = c_B - c_I$. When equations (6a) and (6b) are differentiated and the Van't Hoff relation is substituted, it becomes apparent that

$$\Delta(\Delta H') = 2.303 R (a_B - a_I) + (c_I - c_B) T^2 = 2.303 R (a - cT^2) \quad (8)$$

where, $\Delta(\Delta H') = \Delta H'_B - \Delta H'_I$. It is clear that the last equality in equation (8) may be obtained directly by differentiating equation (7). It further follows that

$$\Delta(\Delta C_p) = -4.606 R cT \quad (9)$$

TABLE 2—DIFFERENCES BETWEEN APPARENT THERMODYNAMIC VALUES FOR THE SYSTEM *m*-NITROPHENOL - HYDRAZENIUM SULPHATE, AS OBTAINED BY THERMOCHROMIC AND POTENTIOMETRIC METHODS

I=0.115 M

T °C	Thermochromic method		Potentiometric method	
	$\Delta(\Delta H) \pm 0.12$ kJ mol ⁻¹	$\Delta(\Delta C'_p) \pm 12$ J K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹	$\Delta(\Delta H') \pm 0.12$ kJ mol ⁻¹	$\Delta(\Delta C'_p) \pm 12$ J K ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
5	27.29	274	27.28	293
15	24.50	283	24.39	301
25	21.62	293	21.67	314
35	18.64	303	18.20	322
45	15.56	313	14.90	335
55	12.38	323	11.47	343

 Fig. 1. $\log R$ against $1/T(K)$ for a solution containing 2.390×10^{-4} M *m*-nitrophenol and 5.000×10^{-3} M hydrazenium sulphate, $I=0.115$ M. The curve is based on a computer fit of the data to equation (4).

where, $\Delta(\Delta C'_p) = \Delta C'_{p(B)} - \Delta C'_{p(I)}$. The optical density—temperature data were fitted to equation (7) by means of the same computer program used earlier for fitting the pK data. The best-fit curve is shown in Fig. 1 alongside the experimental points.

The values obtained for the constants of equation (7) were $a=3\,412$, $b=19.47$ and $c=2.556\,7 \times 10^{-2}$. Thus, for the present buffer—indicator system,

$$\log R = 3\,412/T - 19.47 + (2.567 \times 10^{-2})T \quad (10)$$

Table 2 lists $\Delta(\Delta H')$ and $\Delta(\Delta C'_p)$ as obtained directly from equations (8) and (9) (thermochromic values) and compares them with values obtained from equations (4) and (5) (potentiometric values). The uncertainties in these values were computed by the method of Please⁷. The good correlation between the results of the thermochromic and potentiometric methods indicates that the former may be applied as a powerful tool for obtaining thermodynamic values. Thus, if the relevant values of the indicator are known, for example, the corresponding values for the buffer, although itself non-absorbing, may be easily obtained. Finally, it is noteworthy that the error due to pH measurements is eliminated, since this parameter does not appear in equations (7), (8) and (9).

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